

Auto-calibration and performance monitoring of GRAVITY+ Adaptive Optics system with physics-based methods and inverse problem approaches

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ABSTRACT

In 2024/2025, the GRAVITY+ Adaptive Optics (GPAO) project installed four extreme AO systems on the 8-meter UTs of the Very Large Telescope: 43x43 deformable mirrors (DM, 1432 actuators), 40x40 visible and 30x30 laser guide star Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensors (SH-WFS) with 9x9 infrared or 2x2 visible SH-WFSs for low order sensing. These subsystems are distributed across the entire infrastructure (pupil in M2 rotating with elevation ; DM in Coudé train wobbling and rotating with azimuth ; WFSs fixed on the ground ; science focal plane in the interferometric laboratory 150 meters away). GPAO's complexity prefigures that of the AO systems of future giant telescopes: numerous modes, many moving components, and the need to operate robustly in a broad range of magnitudes and turbulence conditions. GPAO successfully achieved these goals thanks to a complete re-design of the tools available in the Standard Platform for Adaptive optics Real Time Applications (SPARTA, from ESO) and the development of new, versatile methods based on physical modelling and inverse problem approaches. In this work we present the five main modules and their on-sky performances: (i) the Pseudo Synthetic Interaction Matrix (PSIM) module, in charge to numerically (and quickly) compensate the system rotation, which includes a physical model of the ALPAO DM influence functions, (ii) the innovative estimators of WFS/DM lateral mis-registrations for the instrument bootstrapping through the turbulence in open loop and its auto-alignment in closed loop, (iii) a robust spot monitor for faint star detection and centering during the automatic acquisition sequence and for the update of the weighted center of gravity in closed loop, (iv) the atmospheric and performance monitor made versatile to the different GPAO modes and augmented with an innovative multi-layer profiler for wind estimation, and (v) a pupil monitor that offers a fine positioning of the photometric pupil, its orientation and magnification.

Keywords: Auto-calibration ; Performance monitoring ; Acquisition sequence ; Data analysis ; Data processing ; AO telemetry ; Robust methods ; Inverse problem approach ; Physical modelling

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of the GRAVITY+ project, four new extreme Adaptive Optics (AO) systems, so-called GPAOs, have been installed on the four Unit Telescopes (UTs) of the Very Large Telescope Interferometer [VLTi, 16]. Their 43×43 ALPAO Deformable Mirrors (DM, 1432 actuators) are installed below the UT platforms and rotate with the azimuth while the different Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensors (SH-WFS) are fixed in the Coudé room: the 40×40 SH-WFS for visible Natural Guide Star (NGS VIS mode), the 9×9 SH-WFS for infra-red NGS (NGS IR mode), the 30×30 SH-WFS for Laser Guide Star (LGS mode) and its 4×4 low order SH-WFS (LO).

The Real Time Computer (RTC) must handle the system complexity, providing robust and fast methods while not sacrificing the performances in order to acquire the target, optimise the system during the acquisition sequence and then keep the loop closed to its optimal functioning point. The GPAO RTC is based on the Standard Platform for Adaptive optics Real Time Applications [SPARTA, 14, 27, 28] and inherits from the methods developed for the Adaptive Optics Facility [AOF, 20, 21], later improved for the Enhanced Resolution Imager and Spectrograph [ERIS, 2].

In this work, we focus on the methods implemented in the Soft RTC (SRTC), the highest level of the RTC in charge of high-level functions that do not require real time performances but are essential to configure the AO loop, retrieve and analyse its telemetry and communicate with the GPAO Observing System (OS). This is done through specialised modules that model the physics of the AO system. These physical models can be used to actively control the AO loop (generating the control matrix, setting the gains, weight maps, ...) or to monitor its parameters (spot shape, turbulence parameters, ...).

In the following, we present the essential modules that have been adapted, or even fully re-written, for GPAO. In Sec. 2, we present its Pseudo Synthetic Interaction Matrix (PSIM) model that includes a new way to model ALPAO deformable mirrors and major speed improvements from the AOF. For GPAO, we developed new methods to control the lateral registration between the DM and the SH-WFS via a `ShiftMonitor` in order to robustly align the system during the acquisition sequence and keep it closed to its optimal alignment in closed loop. In parallel, the `MisregMonitor` tracks the PSIM mis-registration parameters. These monitors and their performances are discussed in Sec. 3. We re-implemented from scratch a `SpotMonitor` that became the Swiss knife of the acquisition sequence, as detailed in Sec. 4. We introduce in Sec. 5 a new multi-layer frozen flow estimator in the `AtmPerfMonitor` in charge of estimating the atmosphere parameters and the AO loop performances. Finally, we present in Sec. 6 the module in charge to track the photometric pupil parameters.

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The poster of the conference is given after the references.

2. PSEUDO SYNTHETIC INTERACTION MATRIX MODEL

2.1 Model of the 43×43 ALPAO Deformable Mirror Influence Function

The DM model is at the heart of the PSIM module. It is critical that this model can accurately reproduce the membrane shape produced by the DM for any given command. The DM is classically modelled as a linear combination of its actuator influence function φ_a , defined as the 2D shape that takes the membrane when poking only the actuator a , linearly proportional with the applied command. Several studies have shown that this is a good approximation for ALPAO DMs [10, 23].

To model the actuator influence functions themselves, different strategies exist, generally based on empirical analytical profiles, such as Gaussian [26, 29], modified-Gaussian [18], spline [5], cardinal sine [26] or Bessel Fourier Orthogonal Functions [24] among others [6, 19], that are potentially modified to account for the Cartesian to hexagonal geometry of the actuator grid that could break the axisymmetry assumption. However, the actual shapes of influence functions may be more complex and difficult to approach using these analytical models [30].

ALPOA provided high-resolution measurements of the 43×43 DMs (1432 active actuators) procured for the GRAVITY+ project, see Fig. 1a. We used these data to fit an empirical average 2D model of the influence function φ_a^{2D} for each of the six DMs (one for each of the four VLT Unit Telescopes (UT) and two spares). The super-resolved model was obtained through different steps.

Figure 1. Influence function model of the ALPAO DM. Panel a: high resolution measure provided by ALPAO (actuator 96/1432). Panel b: residuals between the empirical 2D influence function model φ_a^{2D} of Panel d and its corresponding super-Gaussian fit φ_a^{SG} of Panel c. Panels e,f: influence function model residuals for the 96th actuator. Panels g,h: wavefront shape produced by a pure piston command. The green ellipse highlights the theoretical 101×98 mm beam footprint on the tilted DM mount and the red circle corresponds to the 108 mm DM clear aperture. Panels c,e,g: super-Gaussian model. Panels d,f,h: 2D empirical model.

First, we fitted an axisymmetric super-Gaussian model φ_a^{SG} for each actuator

$$\varphi_a^{SG}(\mathbf{x}) = \rho_a e^{\alpha_a |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_a|^{-\beta_a}} + \varphi_a^0, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} stands for the 2D coordinate vector, \mathbf{x}_a is the position of the a^{th} actuator, (α_a, β_a) are the parameters of the super-Gaussian profile, ρ_a the actuator gain and φ_a^0 an offset to fit the pedestal on which lies the influence function, the measurement being insensitive to the global membrane piston. Fig. 1e shows the residuals of the fit for the actuator $a = 96$. If most of the pattern is correctly removed, it can clearly be seen that radial super-Gaussian model is too simple: the neighbouring actuators have a strong footprint that breaks the axisymmetric assumption.

Second, the obtained set of position $\{\mathbf{a}\}$ is used to fit the regular Cartesian grid of the actuator position (clocking and pitch), in red in Fig. 1. This grid serves two purposes: (I) it allows to know where are the centres of the actuators lying beyond the measurement aperture (blue circle), (II) it can be used to generate a high-resolution

reference frame within the de-rotated actuator frame. This super-resolved grid is defined with 10 pixels per actuator pitch. For each actuator, the influence function measurement is normalised by ρ_a , removing the offset φ_a^0 and re-interpolated on this grid centred on the actuator position with a radius of 7.5 actuator pitch (green circle). The resulting cube is averaged. Due to the noise on the tip-tilt, this stacked influence function may not be perfectly symmetric and the horizontal and vertical symmetry in the actuator frame is enforced by averaging the 8 transposed and flipped combinations of the 2D stack. This gives the high-resolution empirical 2D influence function φ_0^{2D} of Fig. 1d. It is possible to see that the real influence function has a small negative overshoot that cannot be explained with the axisymmetric super-Gaussian profile (four blue areas). The residuals from Fig. 1f show that this 2D empirical model efficiently fits the actuator cross-coupling.

Figure 1c shows the best super-Gaussian profile fitted in Fig. 1d, and Fig. 1b the corresponding residuals. It shows that an actuator couples with its neighbours up to 3 pitches and up to -5% of the normalised profile. Figures 1g,h focuses on the ability of each model to produce a flat shape when pushing all the actuators. Beyond the gain inhomogeneity visible on Fig. 1g, the super-Gaussian profile produces high spatial frequency peaks that cannot be flattened by any linear combination of the model, emphasising how critical this is for the model to account for the inter-actuator cross-talk. On the opposite, the 2D empirical model reproduces a perfectly flat wavefront.

Important note: in this section, we only presented how to fit the 2D pattern of the average DM influence function. Nonetheless, its fine shape spatially varies with the actuators, and each actuator has its own gain. In the GPAO PSIM model, this is handled by a coupling matrix that mixes this average influence function for each actuator with its neighbours. The diagonal of this matrix corresponds to the individual actuator gains while the non-diagonal terms encompass the inter-actuator coupling as well as local shape variations: at the first order, the individual influence functions are a linear combination of the average zero order 2D empirical model. If this could be done in the ALPAO measurements, this coupling was rather calibrated with the GPAO system on the bench, using the VLTI internal beacon for two reasons: (I) the ALPAO measurements were done on an aperture smaller than clear aperture of the DM that is used in its entirety in GPAO due to the photometric pupil wobble (see Sec. 6), (II) we needed to provide a procedure to monitor the DM evolution and ageing with a solution to update this coupling matrix in the system if necessary. The method to fit this coupling matrix is beyond the scope of this paper and will be presented in an upcoming communication, see Ref. [9].

2.2 PSIM Model and Parameters

For GPAO, the forward model of the SH-WFS to generate the interaction matrix (IM) is canonical: (I) the incident wavefront is mapped on the SH-WFS pixel grid, (II) the 2D slopes of each SH-WFS sub-aperture is computed as the difference between the phase integrated on each opposite side of the corresponding pixel box on the sensor. The boxes are assumed to be adjacent with the same integer number of pixels*. For sub-apertures on the pupil edge, the curved side is accounted for in the slope normalisation. Its implementation in SPARTA for the PSIM module is mainly inherited from ERIS [2], itself inherited from the AOF [20]. Nonetheless, GPAO has a strong timing requirement: its control matrix must be updated in less than 5s for zenith crossing [16]. So compared to Ref. [20], the module has been partly rewritten to improve its performances, and works as follows:

- 1 At the module initialisation, the cube of the 1432 influence functions is generated based on the 2D empirical model of Sec. 2.1 and mixed with the coupling matrix on a grid larger than the pupil to account for possible mis-registrations. The SH-WFS model is also generated: the list of pixels on the sub-aperture edges and their corresponding weights. The influence functions and the SH-WFS model are stored in global variables to be directly available at next call.
- 2 When the module is called to generate a new IM, as for the AOF and for speed efficiency, only a limited number of neighbouring sub-apertures in the vicinity of each actuator is considered. But due to the azimuth rotation between the DM and the SH-WFS, this list is now dynamic, depending on the clocking mis-registration parameter δ_θ . Typical 200 sub-apertures are selected, corresponding to a radius of ~ 8 sub-aperture pitch, in agreement with the 7.5 actuator pitch of the influence function model, see Sec. 2.1.
- 3 The selected sub-apertures are projected in the DM influence function frame by linear interpolation using the faster *griddedInterpolant* function from Matlab®. Improving from the AOF, only the pixels on the edges of the selected sub-aperture are interpolated rather than the full box.

*6 × 6 for the 40 × 40 visible NGS WFS, 8 × 8 for the 30 × 30 LGS WFS, 8 × 8 for the 9 × 9 visible IR WFS, 12 × 12 for the 4 × 4 visible LO WFS.

- 4 The projection accounts for the DM *vs* SH-WFS mis-registrations. Compared to the AOF, the two anamorphoses ($\delta_{X/Y}, \delta_{45}$) have been implemented on top of the generic 2D lateral error (δ_x, δ_y), clocking δ_θ and global magnification δ_ρ , see Fig. 2.
- 5 To avoid the use of time consuming `parfor` loops of the AOF, the full problem is written matrix-vector-wise to benefit from the inherent vectorisation of Matlab[®].
- 7 After the interpolation, the SH-WFS model is applied, computing the weighted edge-to-edge phase differences.

The new PSIM module of GPAO runs in less than 1.5 s on the SPARTA machine for the 40×40 NGS VIS mode, the most demanding configuration of the system (1432 actuators by 2480 slopes).

Figure 2. First three panels: the six mis-registration parameters of the PSIM model: 2D lateral error (δ_x, δ_y), clocking δ_θ , magnification δ_ρ and the two anamorphoses ($\delta_{X/Y}, \delta_{45}$). Fourth panel: anamorphoses fitted on calibration IMs recorded by rotating the UT azimuth for the four GPAOs.

In operation, the lateral error is monitored and controller on-the-fly, see Ref. Sec. 3.2. The other mis-registration parameters need to be calibrated. This was done using the internal beacon of the VLTI by rotating the azimuth. The results are presented in the right panels of Fig. 2 and in Table 1. In this context, δ_θ corresponds of the offset to the clocking angle expected from the known azimuth angle. The error bars of Table 1 show that the PSIM model is extremely sensitive and robust. The table only presents the results for the NGS VIS mode, the value for the other modes are listed in Ref. [16, Tab. B.1] and corresponds to the fourth panel of Fig. 2. The anamorphosis plot of Fig. 2 shows that there is a negligible (below 0.1%) anamorphosis that rotates with the azimuth.

Table 1. Mis-registration parameters fitted on the VLT beacon for the four systems

NGS VIS	GPAO1	GPAO2	GPAO3	GPAO4
δ_ρ (%)	2.784 ± 0.006	3.469 ± 0.006	2.065 ± 0.009	3.465 ± 0.014
δ_θ (°)	0.604 ± 0.004	1.212 ± 0.010	-1.144 ± 0.003	-2.945 ± 0.013

3. SHIFT/MISREGMONITOR - AUTO-CALIBRATION AND MONITORING

The strategy to handle the lateral error registration in GPAO has been extensively detailed in Ref. [4]: a perturbative method is used during the acquisition sequence to centre the star in the SH-WFS field of view (FOV) while a passive method runs in closed loop to monitor and re-align the system on-the-fly. The two approaches have been tested on the GPAO test bench at Nice and with on-sky data from the Center for High Angular Resolution Astronomy (CHARA) and the Coudé Infrared Adaptive Optics (CIAO) before its decommissioning in the context of the GRAVITY+ upgrade, see Ref. [8]. In the following, we present on-sky results of the two methods obtained during GPAO commissioning.

3.1 Lateral Registration During Acquisition

GPAO relies on a implicit modal control based on Karhunen–Loève (KL) functions [13] applied on the DM membrane. As presented in Refs. [4, 8, 16], during the acquisition sequence when the AO loop is still open, these modes are modulated (push-pull disturbance) to record a modal IM. This modal is reshaped in 2D, see Fig. 3a, and compared with the reference centred modal IM via “2D+mode” weighted correlation. At bright end, when the system runs faster than $f \geq 500$ Hz, the 500 first controlled modes are modulated to centre the system below 10% of a sub-aperture. At faint end, when the system runs slower than $f \leq 250$ Hz and controls only the first 200 KL modes, only 1 mode every 9 out the 500 first modes are modulated to centre the system below 25% of

a sub-aperture. This allows speeding up the acquisition while recording high spatial frequency modes for fine centring.

Figure 3. On-sky results of the **ShiftMonitor** at faint end on a 12.1 magnitude star with the system running at **high** gain and 100 Hz. Panels a1,a2: example on the 28th modes of the modulated 2D modal IM and its corresponding measurements. Panel b: correlation of all the system KL modes on the measured modal IM. Green circles emphasise the modulated modes. Panels c1-c4: 2D modal IM correlations for the single 28th mode (c1, dynamic divided by 10), all the non-modulated modes (c2), the full measured modal IM (c3) and with a shifted reference (c4).

Figure 3 introduces an on-sky result when acquiring a 12.1 magnitude star with the system running at **high** gain and 100 Hz. As visible in Fig. 3a2, the single-mode measurement is extremely noisy, with the modulated mode being invisible. The grey sub-apertures correspond to invalid sub-apertures in the model. The resulting correlation map, based solely on this single mode, exhibits numerous maxima, see Fig. 3c1. The correlation coefficients for the centred model for each individual mode of the measured modal IM is also given in Fig. 3b. The modulated modes are marked with a green circle: although very noisy, they are generally distinguishable from the white noise of the unmodulated modes. As indicated in Ref. [4], only combining the full modal IM in a general inverse problem approach collapses the correlation map in a single well-identified peak, as shown in Fig. 3c3. To check that this is not a spurious peak, the correlation map with a shifted synthetic reference is shown in Fig. 3c4. If the background noise changes (due to the shifted valid slopes in the model), the correlation peak remains clearly distinct from the noise.

3.2 Closed Loop Auto-alignment

In GPAO, the DM mount rotates with the azimuth platform while the different SH-WFSs are fixed to the ground. This is prone to mis-alignment and the photometric pupil cannot be used to register the DM relative to the SH-WFSs due to the wobble of the beam on the DM, as discussed in Sec. 6. To follow and actively re-align the pupil with the SH-WFS translating stages, we implemented an innovative and non-invasive approach based on closed telemetry monitoring, detailed in Refs. [4, 8]. In short, in the presence of a lateral mis-alignment, the even part of a given spatial frequency k_{2D} produced by the DM slightly projects on its odd part from the SH-WFS point of view that will consequently send it back to the DM for correction, and oppositely. In the space of the DM 2D commands, there is consequently a beating between the odd and even parts of the spatial frequencies with a characteristic pattern according to the temporal frequency f , shown in green in Fig. 4a. This correlation pattern only depends on the loop parameters (integral and leak gains, frequency, latencies, ...) and is proportional to the spatial frequency, see Fig. 4b.

As discussed in Refs. [4, 8], the bias induced by frozen flow layers in the turbulence is limited but not totally absent. It is visible in Fig. 4a as strong peak around 20 Hz, while the small peak around 90 Hz in the red curve corresponds to the mis-registration signal. As far as this wind-induced peak stays far from the theoretical correlation peak, the impact on the estimated mis-registration is limited. This bias is well visible in the 2D map of Fig. 4c.

Figure 5 gathers different convergence tests of the **ShiftMonitor**, by kicking the translating stage of the SH-WFSs or by changing the loop parameters (in GPAO the AO loop gain depends on the loop frequency and is not an independent parameter). As the encoder values are relative, they were calibrated in terms of reference and amplitude via on-sky calibration IMs (stars on the figure) measured by sending a push-pull Hadamard zonal pattern. These are the plain curves.

For the 40×40 NGS VIS mode, Fig. 5a shows that for a loop frequency lower than $f = 250$ Hz, the secondary loop that controls the pupil mis-registration diverges up to 50% of a sub-aperture (SA) in each direction, so

Figure 4. As detailed in Ref. [4], a lateral mis-registration correlates the 2D DM commands temporal frequency f (a) proportionally to the spatial frequency k_{2D} (b) with a theoretical pattern (green curve) that only depends on the loop parameters. Panel a: the shaded curves correspond to the noisy data after a pupil kick (red) and after convergence (blue) of the **ShiftMonitor**. The non-shaded curves are mean averages with a sliding window of ± 10 Hz. Panel c: at convergence, the residual pattern is due to the bias induced by frozen flow wind layers.

Figure 5. Exercising on-sky the **ShiftMonitor** auto-alignment of the DM/SH-WFS lateral mis-registration. Green-shaded areas correspond to transitions in the test sequence, such as manually kicking the pupil, changing the system frequency, or re-centring the pupil with the perturbative approach of Sec. 3.1. The stars give the x (blue) and y (red) lateral errors measured by fitting the PSIM parameters on a IM recorded on-sky (push-pull Hadamard disturbance). The plain curves are pupil encoder values on both axes, centred and rescaled in percent of sub-aperture based on the on-sky measurements. The dashed curves are the mis-registration values estimated by the **MisregMonitor** on the closed loop telemetry.

70% SA in total. Depending on the wind conditions, not presented here, the system also reached the point where instabilities were triggered in the DM commands (“waffle” modes). Things got worse with $f = 100$ Hz (not shown here). For these frequencies (and associated loop gains), the wind-induced correlation is in the peak of the mis-registration correlation pattern, making the system diverge. This is in agreement with the simulations of Ref. [4]. As a consequence, the pupil auto-alignment was de-activated in GPAO for $f \leq 250$ Hz. On the opposite, Figs. 5a,b show that for $f \geq 500$ Hz, the lateral error is brought back below 25% SA after a pupil kick and stays in this safe zone where the loop works without any issue, even controlling the baseline of 500 modes.

For the 9×9 NGS IR mode, Figs. 5c,d show that for all possible frequencies, the system recovers from a pupil kick and stays in the safe zone of $\pm 25\%$ SA. Once again, the worst case is reached with the lowest frequency of $f \leq 100$ Hz. In the IR mode, the pupil auto-centring in GPAO is thus always activated.

On top of this new **ShiftMonitor**, GPAO also inherited the AOF **MisregMonitor** [20] which implements the method developed in Ref. [3]: based on the correlations between the residual slopes and the DM commands, an IM is estimated from the closed loop telemetry stream. Nonetheless, as discussed in Ref. [17, Sec. 2.1], this method is heavily biased by the wind, and exercising the **ShiftMonitor** was also a good test of the **MisregMonitor**.

3.3 On-sky Mis-registration Monitoring

The **MisregMonitor** highly benefited from the speed improvements implemented for the PSIM model, see Sec. 2.2. Previously limited to run once every 10 min, for GPAO it logs points in the database every 1 min, allowing to perform statistics along the night where before only a sparse amount of points was available for a given science observation. The values gathered during the on-sky test of the **ShiftMonitor** are given by the dashed curves of Fig. 4.

For the 40×40 NGS VIS mode, it clearly appears that the values are totally off for $f \leq 500$ Hz. The **MisregMonitor** provides quantitative results only when the systems runs at the fastest frequency of $f = 1$ kHz. The 9×9 NGS IR mode is less wind sensitive, with quantitative results for $f \geq 500$ Hz.

In total, it appears that the **GPAO ShiftMonitor** is more robust to frozen flow turbulent layers than the **MisregMonitor** from the AOF. For situation where the fine control of the DM/SH-WFS is the most critical (fast correction and 500 controlled modes), the **ShiftMonitor** manages to auto-calibrate the pupil alignment to less than 25 % SA. The system has been in operation on-sky with the settings described in this section, for more than a year at the time of writing, without triggering any loop instability.

Figure 6 gives additional points gathered with the **SpotMonitor** during operations. The clouds seem noisy, but this is coming from points logged during the acquisition sequence or during daytime beacon tests which are consequently outliers. We discuss here only about the trends given by the regions of highest densities. The median values, emphasised with the dashed lines, must be compared with the appendix of Ref. [16, Tab. B.1].

Figure 6. PSIM parameters fitted on-sky by the **MisregMonitor** for the 40×40 NGS VIS and 9×9 NGS IR (first and second line, VLTI run of August 2025, 8 nights) and 30×30 LGS (third line, science verification of March 2026, 2 nights). The clocking error δ_θ is display in terms of the PSIM parameter θ that evolves with the azimuth angle. The magnification parameter δ_ρ is displayed in terms of the elevation. The size of the dots is proportional to the equivalent wind speed v_0 fitted by the **AtmPerfMonitor**, see Sec. 5. The values between parentheses are the median values of each data clouds, also highlighted by the coloured dashed lines.

The first line of Fig. 6 focuses on data acquired in NGS VIS mode during the VLTI science run of August 2025 (8 nights). Looking at the lateral error (δ_x, δ_y), the data point cloud is confined within 25 % SA, the vast majority being even below 10 % SA: this confirms the results from above that the **ShiftMonitor** keeps the mis-registration between the DM and SH-WFS under control with a limited bias by the equivalent wind speed v_0 . Interestingly, the clocking error δ_θ seems to follow a parabolic trend with the azimuth, deviating from the median values to a few tenths of a degree. After investigation, it probably comes from the way the data are logged: they are saved every minute based on the value currently stored in the database. As the **MisregMonitor** also runs once every minute, it is possible to store azimuth values read in the telescope database that are one minute apart from the data time-stamp used by the **MisregMonitor** and stored in its database. When targets cross zenith, this implies possible large errors in the clocking angles. This is supported by the fact that this trend is not visible in Fig. 2

which were recorded on beacon, nor in Fig. 14 as the `PupilMonitor` runs every few seconds. Nonetheless, the median values are in very good agreement with the values of Table 1, calibrated on the VLTI beacon. Below 0.4° , this corresponds to $\sim 15\%$ SA on the pupil edge in NGS VIS. The values on the magnification δ_ρ also agree with the beacon results within 0.3% ($\sim 6\%$ SA on the pupil edge). The anamorphosis errors ($\delta_{X/Y}, \delta_{45}$) are the ones diverging the most from the beacon tests of Sec. 2.2, with a trend clearly not centred on 0 for all GPAOs, around $\delta_{X/Y} \simeq 0.1\%$, with a dispersion of $\pm 0.15\%$ (less than 6% SA on the pupil edge).

The second line of Fig. 6 focuses on data acquired in NGS IR mode during the VLTI science run of August 2025 (8 nights). They confirm that in this mode, the `ShiftMonitor` is not strongly biased by the wind, the lateral errors (δ_x, δ_y) being confined within $\pm 5\%$. The error on the clocking δ_θ seems worse, with strong deviations from the median value, up to more than a degree. Nonetheless, the clocking is poorly constrained on a 9×9 compared to a 40×40 SH-WFS. In addition, the poor fit in the gap between 225° and 300° correspond to the moments at which the target crossed zenith, amplifying the error on the angle mentioned above due to database logging. Despite this, the values are fully compliant with the values of Ref. [16, Tab. B.1]. Surprisingly, the dispersion around the estimated magnification δ_ρ is less scattered, also fully agreeing with Ref. [16, Tab. B.1]. The IR SH-WFS presents strong anamorphoses ($\delta_{X/Y}, \delta_{45}$), here as well in agreement with Ref. [16, Tab. B.1].

Finally, the third line of Fig. 6 focuses on data acquired in LGS mode during the VLTI science verification run of March 2026 (2 nights). Similar conclusions as for the NGS VIS mode can be derived from the LGS data points, with the noticeable difference of the magnification error δ_ρ . A clear trend stands out in function of the elevation. This suggests a cross-coupling between the focusing stage that keeps the sodium layer in focus with the variation of the airmass in function of the elevation and the DM footprint magnification on the LGS SH-WFS. The deviation from the median is below 2.5% , corresponding to less than 4% SA on the LGS pupil edge. As for the NGS VIS mode, the anamorphoses are negligible. In LGS mode, the system always runs at 1 kHz, meaning that the `ShiftMonitor` is robust to wind and that the `MisregMonitor` is quantitative: the lateral error seems mostly constrained within $\pm 5\%$ SA with a few excursion up to $\sim 10\%$ SA. Let us nonetheless note that the wind estimated by the `AtmPerfMonitor` was slow during these two nights with $3 \text{ m s}^{-1} \leq v_0 \leq 8 \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

4. SPOTMONITOR - ROBUST SPOT DETECTION AND MONITORING

4.1 Context and Spot Model

In the AOF [20, 21], the role of the `SpotMonitor` was mainly to generate the weight maps for the weighted centre of gravity of the AO loop. This weight map was based on a fixed size, or fed by the spot size measured by the monitor on an average pixel frame obtained from the AO telemetry stream. The spot pattern could either be a 2D elongated Gaussian or a Moffat. The parameters of the spots (size, amplitude, orientation, elongation) were fitted independently in each sub-aperture box, a method extremely sensitive to noise. For LGS acquisition, the spot elongation was used to retrieve the thickness of the sodium layer.

For GPAO, the module has been deeply re-written, to handle all the GPAO SH-WFS geometries and to provide new functionalities. If the AOF monitoring is still provided but with a more robust estimator, as discussed in Sec. 4.3, a new feature for spot detection and centring has been also developed and became a central part of the GPAO automatic acquisition sequence, as described in Sec. 4.2.

Following the experience feedback from the AOF, GPAO `SpotMonitor` only relies on an elongated 2D Gaussian spot model:

$$\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{x}_0, \Theta, \alpha, \beta) = \alpha g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta) + \beta, \quad (2)$$

where $\Theta = (\Theta_{\text{NE}}, \Theta_{\text{E}}, \theta)$ are the elongation and orientation parameters, \mathbf{x}_0 the 2D position of the spot centre in the pixel frame of 2D coordinates $\mathbf{x} = (x, y)$, α its amplitude and β its offset[†]. g is the 2D Gaussian function

$$g(\mathbf{x}, \Theta) = \exp \left[-4 \ln 2 \left(\frac{(x \cos \theta - y \sin \theta)^2}{\Theta_{\text{NE}}^2} + \frac{(x \sin \theta + y \cos \theta)^2}{\Theta_{\text{NE}}^2 + \Theta_{\text{E}}^2} \right) \right]. \quad (3)$$

We insist here that Θ_{NE} is the full width at half-maximum along the non-elongated axis while the Θ_{E} parameter quadratically adds to Θ_{NE} on the elongated axis: its elongated full width at half-maximum is $\sqrt{\Theta_{\text{NE}}^2 + \Theta_{\text{E}}^2}$. In practice, to compensate for the fact that the spots are described on only a limited number of pixels, the model is generated on an over-sampled grid by a factor $\times 4$ that is then binned at the pixel box resolution. Let us note here that the spot flux is given by the integral of this over-sampled model, not by its amplitude α which does not integrate the spot shape Θ .

[†]In a well calibrated system, after the dark (or the sky in the presence of the moon) removal, $\beta \simeq 0$. But SPARTA performs 0-clipping before averaging, producing a global pedestal in the pixel frame.

If \mathbf{d} is the data sensor map, we note \mathbf{d}_ℓ the ℓ^{th} sub-aperture pixel box (ℓ stands for lenslet), \mathbf{w}_ℓ its valid pixel map and \mathcal{V} the subset of valid sub-aperture. Noting \mathbf{p} the list of all sub-aperture parameters, fitting the spot models in the SH-WFS pixel data formally writes as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{p}} = \underset{\mathbf{p}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left[\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{p}) = \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}} \|\mathbf{d}_\ell - \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{p}_\ell)\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell} \right] \text{ with } \|\mathbf{f}\|_{\mathbf{w}} = \sum_{\mathbf{x} \in \text{box}} w(\mathbf{x})[f(\mathbf{x})]^2. \quad (4)$$

We keep the notation \mathbf{p} ambiguous as its definition will depend on the situation, as discussed in Secs. 4.2 and 4.3.

As a final remark, the `SpotMonitor` is the only GPAO SPARTA module that has access to the SH-WFS pixel. We do not present in this paper other functionalities that have been (I) implemented, such as a white stripe detector to identify issues with the OCAM2 clocking triggering aberrant column readings on the sensor, or (II) discussed and de-scoped, such as using the `SpotMonitor` to extract the intensities in the sub-aperture outside the SH-WFS boxes defined for the RTC, or look at the spot splitting behind the spider in the presence of low wind effect [25] to estimate the pupil quadrant de-phasing.

4.2 Robust Star Detection and Centring: Common Spot Fitting

To account for possible errors in the target magnitude (error in the observation preparation, variable stars, ...) and avoid any over-illumination of the cameras, the initial settings during an acquisition are conservative, with a camera running slowly and at low gain. This represents two challenges for the automatic acquisition sequence: working against the fast open loop turbulence, and with a high level of noise. Thus, GPAO needed a tool to robustly detect the presence of a star in open loop to trigger or not a raster search, and once the target found, to estimate its magnitude and centre it in the SH-WFS boxes before the camera gain ramp-up.

4.2.1 Fitting a mean spot

A new functionality in the `SpotMonitor` to measure a mean non-elongated spot across all the sub-apertures at once has been implemented:

$$\forall \ell, \alpha_\ell = \alpha, \beta_\ell = \beta, \mathbf{x}_{0,\ell} = \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta_\ell = (\Theta_{\text{NE}}, 0, 0). \quad (5)$$

The minimisation of Eq. (4) now writes as

$$\left(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0, \tilde{\Theta}_{\text{NE}} \right) = \underset{\alpha, \beta, \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta_{\text{NE}}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}} \|\mathbf{d}_\ell - [\alpha g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta) + \beta]\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell}, \quad (6)$$

under the constraints that

$$\alpha \geq 0, \beta \geq 0, \mathbf{x}_0 \in \text{FOV}, \Theta_{\text{NE}} \in [0, \Theta_{\text{NE}}^{\text{max}}]. \quad (7)$$

To avoid any degeneracy between a large spot and the background offset β , the maximal admissible spot size is defined as $\Theta_{\text{NE}}^{\text{max}} = 3/4$ of the box size. To maximise the signal to noise ratio (SNR), all the SH-WFS sub-apertures are used for \mathcal{V} .

In the absence of reference slopes and dead pixels, this boils down to work on the equivalent box obtained by stacking all the sub-apertures together. Viewed like this, it is understandable that the method is highly robust to noise, since for example in NGS VIS, this is averaging the noisy 1240 sub-apertures into a single spot. Examples of such averaged spots are given in Fig. 7c1 (LO) and Fig. 8c1 (NGS IR). It is clearly visible that the SNR is greatly increased when working on all sub-apertures compared to Panel a1.

Nonetheless, such an average image does not exist in a more complex situation, such as the so-called ‘‘disco mode’’ where a strong focus mode is applied in the DM to enhance the FOV probed by the SH-WFS sub-apertures to find the star. In this context, this is equivalent to add offsets \mathbf{x}_ℓ in the model that linearly increase with the radial position of the sub-apertures:

$$\left(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0, \tilde{\Theta}_{\text{NE}} \right) = \underset{\alpha, \beta, \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta_{\text{NE}}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}} \|\mathbf{d}_\ell - [\alpha g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_\ell - \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta) + \beta]\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell}. \quad (8)$$

In this context, it becomes impossible to easily stack the sub-apertures in an equivalent frame to fit the spot position that must be then fitted through the global inverse approach formalism. Figure 9c1 shows an equivalent spot obtained by a weighted stack with nearest pixel interpolation. We insist here that it is given for information but not used for the fit which is done across all the sub-apertures at once in the cost function.

Figure 7. Example of the **SpotMonitor** mean fit on a 18 magnitude star with the LO running at 100 Hz. Panel a1: full pixel frame. Panel a2: fit residuals. Panel a3: map of the valid pixel (dead pixels and FOV). Panels b1-b3: map of the analytical fit to find the best starting point that minimises the cost (b1) and the associated amplitude (b2) and offset (b3). Panels c1-c4: resulting equivalent box maps of the fit with the weighted average spot (c1), model+pedestal (c2) and residuals (c3). Panel c4: map on which the detection SNR is computed. The numbers on the top right and bottom left corners of the gray maps are the maximum and minimal values of the grey colour scale.

Figure 8. Example of the **SpotMonitor** mean fit with the NGS IR mode. See caption of Fig. 7.

Figure 9. Example of the **SpotMonitor** mean fit with the NGS VIS disco mode. See caption of Fig. 7, with the difference that the fit maps (c1, c2, c3) stack the sub-aperture boxes via nearest neighbour interpolation.

Equation (6) (or Eq. (8) if using the disco mode) is solved with the Trust-Region-Reflective method of Refs. [12, 11] (`lsqcurvefit`[‡] in Matlab[®]). Once the parameters of the mean spot are estimated, the amplitude in each sub-aperture has an analytical solution

$$\forall \ell, \tilde{\alpha}_\ell = \frac{\sum_{\mathbf{x} \in \text{box}} w_\ell(\mathbf{x})(d_\ell(\mathbf{x}) - \beta)g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta_{\text{NE}})}{\|g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta_{\text{NE}})\|_{w_\ell}}. \quad (9)$$

The overall fit is consequently extremely fast. The residuals of Panels a2,c3 in the different figures confirm that the 2D symmetric Gaussian pattern is a good approximation of the open-loop mean spot. Let us also remark that the Panels a3 show the valid pixel map, used to encode the sub-aperture FOV or dead pixels. For the LO, where the sky background due to the moon can be quite bright, see Fig. 7a3, this map is needed to discard the corner and avoid biasing the estimation of the offset β .

[‡]Let us remark here that the algorithm only handles bounds which are independent on all the optimised parameters. For non-square fields of view, we multiply the model into brackets in Eqs. (6) and (8) by an indicator function $\mathbf{1}_{\text{fov}}(\mathbf{x}) = 1$ if \mathbf{x} is in the FOV or 0 otherwise. Doing so, a solution outside the FOV will always give a worse cost function than a solution inside and won't be favour by the optimisation algorithm.

4.2.2 Fit initialisation

For the LO, the RTC only uses the central 12×12 pixels of each green box of Figs. 7a to close the AO loop. But the `SpotMonitor` having access to the full sensor, it can cleverly use the full FOV to find and centre the target with a large capture range. In this context, the initial guess to solve Eq. (6) is critical as the optimisation method is highly sensitive to local minima. It is thus necessary to get a first estimation of the spot parameters, in particular its rough position. Using the brightest pixel is not option in poor SNR conditions.

Noting $\Theta_{\text{NE}}^0 = \Theta_{\text{NE}}^{\text{max}}/4$ the initial guess size, the idea is to quickly test all the positions \mathbf{x}_0 in the FOV of $g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta_{\text{NE}}^0)$. Let us introduce

$$c^w = \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}, \mathbf{x} \in \text{box}} w_\ell(\mathbf{x}), \quad c^{\text{wd}} = \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}, \mathbf{x} \in \text{box}} w_\ell(\mathbf{x})d_\ell(\mathbf{x}), \quad c^{\text{wdd}} = \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}, \mathbf{x} \in \text{box}} w_\ell(\mathbf{x})[d_\ell(\mathbf{x})]^2 \quad (10)$$

$$c^{\text{wg}}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}, \mathbf{x} \in \text{box}} w_\ell(\mathbf{x})g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta_{\text{NE}}^0), \quad c^{\text{wgd}}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}, \mathbf{x} \in \text{box}} w_\ell(\mathbf{x})g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta_{\text{NE}}^0)d_\ell(\mathbf{x}) \quad (11)$$

$$c^{\text{wgg}}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}, \mathbf{x} \in \text{box}} w_\ell(\mathbf{x})[g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, \Theta_{\text{NE}}^0)]^2. \quad (12)$$

The optimal amplitude and offset have an analytical solution:

$$\tilde{\alpha}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \frac{c^{\text{wgd}}(\mathbf{x}_0)c^w - c^{\text{wg}}(\mathbf{x}_0)c^{\text{wd}}}{c^w c^{\text{wgg}}(\mathbf{x}_0) - [c^{\text{wg}}(\mathbf{x}_0)]^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\beta}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \frac{c^{\text{wgg}}(\mathbf{x}_0)c^{\text{wd}} - c^{\text{wgd}}(\mathbf{x}_0)c^{\text{wg}}(\mathbf{x}_0)}{c^w c^{\text{wgg}}(\mathbf{x}_0) - [c^{\text{wg}}(\mathbf{x}_0)]^2}. \quad (13)$$

And applying the bounds $(\alpha_{\text{min}}, \beta_{\text{min}})$ if needed:

$$\begin{cases} \text{if } \tilde{\alpha}(\mathbf{x}_0) < \alpha_{\text{min}}, \tilde{\alpha}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \alpha_{\text{min}} \text{ and } \tilde{\beta}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \max\left(\beta_{\text{min}}, \frac{c^{\text{wd}} - \alpha_{\text{min}}c^{\text{wg}}(\mathbf{x}_0)}{c^w}\right) \\ \text{if } \tilde{\beta}(\mathbf{x}_0) < \beta_{\text{min}}, \tilde{\beta}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \beta_{\text{min}} \text{ and } \tilde{\alpha}(\mathbf{x}_0) = \max\left(\alpha_{\text{min}}, \frac{c^{\text{wgd}}(\mathbf{x}_0) - \beta_{\text{min}}c^{\text{wg}}(\mathbf{x}_0)}{c^{\text{wgg}}(\mathbf{x}_0)}\right) \end{cases}. \quad (14)$$

Looking carefully at the coefficients $c^{\text{wg}}(\mathbf{x}_0)$, $c^{\text{wgd}}(\mathbf{x}_0)$ and $c^{\text{wgg}}(\mathbf{x}_0)$, one can see that they are of the shape $\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}, \mathbf{x} \in \text{box}} f(\mathbf{x})h(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)$ which is a correlation that can be computed with correctly 0-padded fast Fourier transform. The 2D cost map $\mathcal{C}(\tilde{\alpha}(\mathbf{x}_0), \tilde{\beta}(\mathbf{x}_0))$ is thus extremely fast to compute on the full FOV.

The global minimum of the cost function is clear on the Panel b1 of Figs. 7, 8 and 9. Its counter-part is also clearly identifiable in the best amplitude and offset maps of Panel b2 and Panel b3. Thus, the iterative fit is simply initialised with

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0^0 = \underset{\mathbf{x}_0}{\text{argmin}} \mathcal{C}(\tilde{\alpha}(\mathbf{x}_0), \tilde{\beta}(\mathbf{x}_0)), \quad \tilde{\alpha}^0 = \tilde{\alpha}(\mathbf{x}_0^0), \quad \tilde{\beta}^0 = \tilde{\beta}(\mathbf{x}_0^0). \quad (15)$$

4.2.3 Proxy for the detection SNR

Once a spot has been fitted, the next question is to know if it is statistically significant or not. To do so, we build the SNR map of Panel c4 of Figs. 7, 8 and 9: it is the amplitude at which the same spot

$$\tilde{m}(\mathbf{x}) = \tilde{\alpha}g(\mathbf{x}, \tilde{\Theta}_{\text{NE}}) \quad (16)$$

would be found again in the residuals

$$\tilde{r}_\ell(\mathbf{x}) = d_\ell(\mathbf{x}) - \tilde{m}(\mathbf{x} - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0) - \tilde{\beta}. \quad (17)$$

It is a simple amplitude computation and has the same analytical shape as Eq. (9)

$$\gamma(\mathbf{x}_0) = \frac{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}, \mathbf{x} \in \text{box}} w_\ell(\mathbf{x})\tilde{r}_\ell(\mathbf{x})\tilde{m}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)}{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}, \mathbf{x} \in \text{box}} w_\ell(\mathbf{x})[\tilde{m}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)]^2}, \quad (18)$$

and can be computed with fast Fourier transform.

The proxy for the detection SNR is then given by $1/\langle \gamma(\mathbf{x}_0) \rangle_{\mathbf{x}_0 \in \text{fov}}$ where $\langle f(\mathbf{x}) \rangle_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}}$ is the standard deviation of f for $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$. The values for the different cases of Figs. 7, 8 and 9 are given in the label of Panel c4. For the LO and NGS IR modes, the detection is credited with a huge SNR, showing the efficiency of the method to detect a spot among the noisy sub-apertures. The result is a bit less favourable in the case of the disco mode in NGS

VIS: if the spot was obvious in the cost map of Fig. 9b1, the detection is only credited with a score of SNR=2.1 . Looking at the residuals of Fig. 9a2, this is understandable: the model poorly fits the data, potentially due to a mismatch between the actual shape of the DM and the naive linear shifts introduced in Eq. (8) for a perfect defocus. Nonetheless, the method still manages to locate the spot and the on-sky tests of the disco mode showed that the star detection and centring converge.

As side remarks, in GPAO, the disco mode was de-scoped after the recalibration of the UTs' pointing model and the improvement on the GPAO raster function. Similarly, the SNR proxy was implemented to provide a tool estimating the confidence on the presence or not of a star in the FOV. But at the end, after the calibration of the look-up table of the camera settings with the target magnitude, a criterion on the spot flux estimated on the mean spot model was sufficient.

4.3 Spot Monitoring: Global Model Fitting

When the system runs in closed loop, the **SpotMonitor** is used to robustly measure the spot parameters. Initially, this was supposed to feed the weight map model at faint end in order to have a weight size that dynamically adapts to the seeing condition or the size of the target for extended objects. This was de-scoped during commissioning. As of now, the closed loop **SpotMonitor** is only used as a monitoring tool, dynamically generating the weight maps with fixed configured shapes (but dynamic reference slopes). As described in the different sections below, Eq. (4) is adapted to the different needs. Table 2 summarises the independent and shared parameters of all cases.

Table 2. Different fitting options of the **SpotMonitor** in closed loop.

Method	Independent parameters	Shared parameters $\forall \ell$
INDEP	$\mathbf{x}_{0,\ell}, \alpha_\ell, \Theta_\ell = (\Theta_{NE,\ell}, \Theta_{E,\ell}, \theta_\ell)$	β
JOINT	$\mathbf{x}_{0,\ell}, \alpha_\ell$	$\Theta = (\Theta_{NE}, 0, 0), \beta$
JOINT_ELONG	$\mathbf{x}_{0,\ell}, \alpha_\ell$	$\Theta = (\Theta_{NE}, \Theta_E, \theta), \beta$
LGS	$\mathbf{x}_{0,\ell}, \alpha_\ell$	$\Theta_{NE}, \Delta_{NA}, \beta$

4.3.1 INDEP - Independent fit for each sub-aperture

The INDEP option fits a 2D elongated pattern for each sub-aperture independently. The only shared parameter is the global offset β . The fit is performed by alternating thrice the following steps:

$$\text{Step 1 - } \forall \ell, (\tilde{\alpha}_\ell, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{0,\ell}, \tilde{\theta}_\ell) = \underset{\alpha, \mathbf{x}_0, \theta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\| \mathbf{d}_\ell - \left[\alpha g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, (\tilde{\Theta}_{NE,\ell}, \tilde{\Theta}_{E,\ell}, \theta)) + \tilde{\beta} \right] \right\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell}, \quad (19)$$

$$\text{Step 2 - } \forall \ell, (\tilde{\alpha}_\ell, \tilde{\Theta}_{NE,\ell}, \tilde{\Theta}_{E,\ell}) = \underset{\alpha, \Theta_{NE}, \Theta_E}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\| \mathbf{d}_\ell - \left[\alpha g(\mathbf{x} - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{0,\ell}, (\Theta_{NE}, \Theta_E, \tilde{\theta}_\ell)) + \tilde{\beta} \right] \right\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell}, \quad (20)$$

$$\text{Step 3 - } \tilde{\beta} = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}} \left\| \mathbf{d}_\ell - \left[\tilde{\alpha}_\ell g(\mathbf{x} - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{0,\ell}, (\tilde{\Theta}_{NE,\ell}, \tilde{\Theta}_{E,\ell}, \tilde{\theta}_\ell)) + \beta \right] \right\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell}. \quad (21)$$

This methods was initially designed for the low order SH-WFSs, namely the 4×4 LO and 9×9 IR SH-WFSs. Indeed, the sub-apertures on the edges are impacted by the sub-aperture truncation by the circular pupil, producing elongated spots. This mode was implemented but de-scoped: (I) this mode is poorly robust to noise, (II) slow because the Steps 1 and 2 are done individually on all the sub-apertures using a **parfor** loop and (III) the spots on the corners of the SH-WFS grids are not used to closed the loop due to their limited and aberrated fields of view. As the remaining spots are from almost fully illuminated sub-apertures, using the **JOINT** option proved to be more adapted, faster and more robust to noise.

4.3.2 JOINT - Symmetric spot across all sub-apertures

The **JOINT** option fits a 2D symmetric pattern ($\Theta_E = 0$) jointly for all sub-apertures in the valid subset \mathcal{V} . The shared parameters are the spot size Θ_{NE} and the global offset β . The fit is performed by alternating thrice

the following steps:

$$\text{Step 1 - } \left(\bar{\alpha}, \tilde{\Theta}_{\text{NE}}, \tilde{\beta} \right) = \underset{\alpha, \Theta_{\text{NE}}, \beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}} \left\| \mathbf{d}_\ell - [\alpha \bar{\alpha}_\ell g(\mathbf{x} - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{0,\ell}, (\Theta_{\text{NE}}, 0, 0)) + \beta] \right\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell}, \quad (22)$$

$$\text{Step 2 - } \forall \ell, (\bar{\alpha}_\ell, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{0,\ell}) = \underset{\alpha, \mathbf{x}_0}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\| \mathbf{d}_\ell - \left[\bar{\alpha} \alpha g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, (\tilde{\Theta}_{\text{NE},0,0}) + \tilde{\beta}) \right] \right\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell}, \quad (23)$$

where $\bar{\alpha}$ is the average spot amplitude across all the valid sub-apertures and $\bar{\alpha}_\ell$ fits their amplitude granularity. The final individual amplitudes are $\tilde{\alpha}_\ell = \bar{\alpha} \bar{\alpha}_\ell$. The limiting factor is Step 2 which is done independently on all sub-apertures. To save time, because the method is very robust to noise, only a subset of all the SH-WFS sub-apertures is used, typically a doughnut to avoid the inner and outer edges where partially illuminated sub-apertures could be found depending on the photometric pupil magnification and wobble, see Figs. 10b2,b4.

Another option would be to force the position $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{0,\ell}$ to be equal to the reference slopes. Indeed, in closed loop, the spots are supposed to be on their reference slopes. In this situation, Step 2 only consists in fitting the individual amplitudes, which has an analytical solution, see Eq. (9) that can be computed using Matlab[®] vectorisation (single pass computing all sub-apertures at once). We did not implement this option in GPAO because we wanted to keep the possibility to fit the individual positions that could diverge from the reference slopes: non-optimal number of controlled modes, bias in the weighted centre of gravity and hidden Non-Common Path Aberrations (NCPA), ...

Compared to the AOF, this implementation runs faster, permitting a logging every 15s. Despite freeing the position parameters for each sub-aperture $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{0,\ell}$ compared to the mean method of Sec. 4.2, the JOINT fit also proved to be really robust to noise, especially on dim targets at faint end.

4.3.3 JOINT_ELONG - Elongated spot across all sub-apertures

The JOINT_ELONG option is a natural extension of the JOINT method which fits an elongated pattern jointly for all sub-apertures in the valid subset \mathcal{V} . The shared parameter are the spot parameters $\Theta = (\Theta_{\text{NE}}, \Theta_{\text{E}}, \theta)$ and the global offset β . The fit is performed by alternating thrice the following steps:

$$\text{Step 1 - } \left(\bar{\alpha}, \tilde{\Theta}, \tilde{\beta} \right) = \underset{\alpha, \Theta, \beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}} \left\| \mathbf{d}_\ell - [\alpha \bar{\alpha}_\ell g(\mathbf{x} - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{0,\ell}, \Theta) + \beta] \right\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell}, \quad (24)$$

$$\text{Step 2 - } \forall \ell, (\bar{\alpha}_\ell, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{0,\ell}) = \underset{\alpha, \mathbf{x}_0}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\| \mathbf{d}_\ell - \left[\bar{\alpha} \alpha g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, \tilde{\Theta}) + \tilde{\beta} \right] \right\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell}, \quad (25)$$

using the same notations as in the previous section. The limiting factor stays Step 2 and the same comments apply as for the JOINT approach.

If this method was implemented in the SRTC, it is not currently used. Discussions are on-going in the consortium to make it available for extended targets and dynamic update of the weight map.

4.3.4 LGS - Robust fit of the sodium layer across all sub-apertures

It is well known that the SH-WFS sub-apertures resolve the sodium layer, producing elongated spots on the detector. The spot elongation and orientation depend on the position of the sub-aperture relative to the laser launch telescope (LLT) placed on the pupil edge. Thus the spot shape parameters vary across the pupil: the JOINT and JOINT_ELONG methods cannot be used while the INDEP fit seems under-optimal and not robust to noise.

Figure 10a introduces a scheme of the situation, with the distance of the sub-aperture to the LLT ρ_ℓ , the airmass parameter χ , the thickness of the sodium layer thickness Δ_{NA} and its height h_{NA} . Under the approximation of small angles, and using the intercept theorem, it comes

$$\frac{\chi h_{\text{NA}} \Theta_{\text{E},\ell}}{\rho_\ell} \simeq \frac{\chi \Delta_{\text{NA}}}{\chi h_{\text{NA}}} \Rightarrow \Theta_{\text{E},\ell}(\Delta_{\text{NA}}) \simeq \frac{\rho_\ell}{\chi h_{\text{NA}}^2} \Delta_{\text{NA}}. \quad (26)$$

Due to the degeneracy between the sodium layer thickness and height, we work under the assumption that $h_{\text{NA}} = 85$ km.

As the geometry of the system is known (ρ_ℓ and $\theta_{\text{LLT},\ell}$ are given by the sub-aperture position relative to the LLT), the elongation across all the sub-apertures thus only depends on one free parameter: the sodium

Figure 10. Comparing the **SpotMonitor** global fit in LGS mode on single frames and 50 frames averages. Panel a: Schematic of the sodium layer seen by a sub-aperture ℓ . Panels b1-b4: examples of pixel frames (b1,b3) and residuals (b2,b4) for a single noisy frame (b1,b2) and an average of 50 consecutive frames (b3,b4). Panels c1-c3: fitted values for different frame numbers: the spot size Θ_{NE} (c1), the sodium layer thickness Δ_{NA} (c2) and the flux (c3). The blue curves are the values obtained by averaging blocks of 50 consecutive frames. The grey curves show the values fitted on the individual frame and the black curves median filters on a sliding window of 50 frames. The dashed lines indicate the mean values of each curve.

layer thickness Δ_{NA} . It can consequently be robustly fitted across all the valid sub-apertures, alongside with the spot size Θ_{NE} (related to the seeing and the jitter residuals) and the global offset β . The fit is performed by alternating thrice the following steps:

$$\text{Step 1} - (\bar{\alpha}, \bar{\Theta}_{\text{NE}}, \bar{\Delta}_{\text{NA}}, \bar{\beta}) = \underset{\alpha, \Theta_{\text{NE}}, \Delta_{\text{NA}}, \beta}{\text{argmin}} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}} \|\mathbf{d}_\ell - [\alpha \bar{\alpha}_\ell g(\mathbf{x} - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{0,\ell}, (\Theta_{\text{NE}}, \Theta_{E,\ell}(\Delta_{\text{NA}}), \theta_{\text{LLT},\ell})) + \beta]\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell}, \quad (27)$$

$$\text{Step 2} - \forall \ell, (\bar{\alpha}_\ell, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{0,\ell}) = \underset{\alpha, \mathbf{x}_0}{\text{argmin}} \left\| \mathbf{d}_\ell - [\bar{\alpha}_\ell g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0, (\bar{\Theta}_{\text{NE}}, \bar{\Delta}_{\text{NA}}, \theta_{\text{LLT},\ell}) + \bar{\beta})] \right\|_{\mathbf{w}_\ell}, \quad (28)$$

using the same notations as in the previous sections. The limiting factor stays Step 2 and the same comments apply as for the **JOINT** and **JOINT_ELONG** approaches.

Figure 10b4 shows the residuals of the fit on the doughnut subset mentioned earlier on the 50 frame average of Fig. 10b3. If some structures can be seen in the residuals, they are at a negligible level compared to the spot full dynamics. This supports the validity of the proposed elongated model, based on a parametric 2D Gaussian profile. Figures 10b1,b2 highlights the robustness of the method on a single noisy frame. This is further supported by Figs. 10c1,c2,c3 which compare the fitted parameters on the individual frames of a sequence (grey) and by stacking successive batches of 50 frames (blue). The black curves are the median filters of the grey curves with a sliding window of 50 frames.

The temporal trend of the parameters fitted on single frames quantitatively follows the trend of the parameters fitted on the 50 frames averages, but with a small offset. The offset on the spot size Θ_{NE} can be interpreted as the residual jitter that is averaged by the 50 frame stacks while it is frozen on the single frame acquisitions. The bias in the sodium layer thickness Δ_{NA} could be linked to fast changes in the sodium layer structure, de-excitation and re-pumping. Finally, the bias in the flux is surely related to the SPARTA noise 0-clipping that biases the offset pedestal and the averaging of the faint spot extensions that can be lost when the photon noise is at the same level as the readout noise. These biases were not deemed critical and the 50 frame average was set as the default parameter of the LGS method.

5. ATMPERFMONITOR - TURBULENCE CHARACTERISATION

The **AtmPerfMonitor** was directly inherited from the AOF without change in its behaviour. As described in Ref. [20], it fits the main turbulence parameters (r_0 , L_0 , seeing, residual variances and estimated Strehl, ...) from the closed loop telemetry implementing the methods of [1, 15]. On top of these existing functionalities, a brand new multi-layer wind estimator has been developed, further described in [7], providing two new outputs: the equivalent wind speed v_0 and coherence time τ_0 .

The module relies on the computation of the pseudo-open loop (POL) slopes, combining the DM commands applied to the PSIM model with the residual slopes on the SH-WFS. To compute the turbulence strength, these POL slopes are then projected on the Zernike modes to compute their temporal variance, as shown in Fig. 11a. This projection is sensitive to SH-WFS aliasing and thus this reconstruction is done on more modes than the atmosphere model fitted to retrieve the turbulence parameters (vertical dashed line). As seen on the figure, the theoretical power law (bold lines) nicely fits the on-sky measurements (dotted lines), in all modes, even in IR where only 5 radial orders out of the 7 reconstructed (15 radial orders fitted among 20 reconstructed for LGS and NGS VIS modes).

Figure 11. Overview of the **AtmPerfMonitor**. Panel a: Variance of the Zernike modes from the POL slopes for the different GPAO modes. To avoid aliasing the modal projection is done on more modes than the subset used for the model fitting (vertical dashed lines). Panels b1-b6: the monitor includes a new multi-layer wind estimator, each turbulent layer producing a peak (green circles) in the POL slopes auto-correlation (b1,b2,b3), as well as smooth translating patterns that are fitted by the model and which thus disappear from the residuals (b4,b5,b6). Panel c: seeing estimated by the **AtmPerfMonitor** in different situations: 9×9 NGS IR (circles), 40×40 NGS VIS (diamonds), 30×30 LGS (triangles), compared to the DIMM (squares). The different colours emphasise the different GPAOs.

Figure 11c compares the fitted seeing by the **AtmPerfMonitor** with the measures from the Differential Image Motion Monitor (DIMM) obtained through different nights. As expected, the UTs pointing all in the same

direction, the four GPAOs stay consistent, the differences being in the measurement noise. To help the comparison, mean average on a sliding window of ± 5 min is given by the plain curves. The estimated seeing mostly matches the seeing delivered by the DIMM with some deviations (such as for the beginning of the night of 2025-08-07) that could be explained by the fact that the DIMM can point in a direction very different from the UTs. For the nights where both NGS VIS and NGS IR observations were performed (2025-08-04 and 2025-08-07), the continuity in the seeing trend is convincing.

The plot of the night of 2025-07-28 shows a unique situation: obtained during a technical time, it compares GPAO1 running in NGS VIS while GPAO4 was in LGS mode. It seems that the LGS cone effect had a negligible impact on the estimated seeing, both curves being in good agreement. It is harder to draw a conclusion on the full LGS night of 2025-03-10 obtained during the LGS science verification: at the beginning of the night, the seeing seems overestimated, and ends being underestimated. But the trends are mostly matching.

Figure 11b presents examples of the multi-layer wind estimator in the different modes. The top line shows a given frame of the temporal 2D auto-correlation of the POL slopes. Frozen flow layers appear as correlation peaks in the 2D maps that translate with time. With its limited resolution, the NGS IR is generally sensitive to the main layer, here moving at 14 m s^{-1} . With their higher resolution, the LGS and NGS VIS allow retrieving several sharp auto-correlation peaks. In Fig. 11b2, the two fastest peak moves at 9 and 18 m s^{-1} . In Fig. 11b3, beyond the central immobile peak, the two strong frozen flow layers have a speed of 5 and 15 m s^{-1} . The estimator fits the global structure of the translating 2D correlation maps: the quality of the residuals show that the frozen flow hypothesis is surprisingly accurate, with most of the turbulence energy being carried by the fitted layers.

6. PUPILMONITOR - FOLLOWING THE PHOTOMETRIC PUPIL

The role of the `PupilMonitor` is to fit the photometric pupil geometry based on the intensities ι_ℓ delivered by the `LoopMonitor`, the module in charge to dispatch the real time data stream to the different modules of the SRTC, see Figs. 12a1,b1,c1. The module inherited from ERIS only fitted an obstructed pupil of fixed size. The GPAO module was entirely rewritten to perform an inverse problem approach including the VLT spider in the pupil model, see Figs. 12a2,b2,c2. This super-resolved model is binned to the SH-WFS resolution $m_\ell^{\text{pup}}(\mathbf{x})$.

On top of the lateral position parameters $\mathbf{x}_\delta = (\delta_x, \delta_y)$, the new method fits the angle θ and magnification ρ of the photometric pupil[§]. Looking at Figs. 12a1c1, eight regions of different intensities can clearly be identified. These correspond to the OCAM2 octants[¶] $\mathcal{V}_{o \in [1,8]}$ and their individual gain g_o . This inhomogeneity is also included in the model, see Figs. 12a3c3, by fitting these gains $g_o(\mathbf{x}_\delta, \theta, \rho)$ on-the-fly in the cost function

$$\left(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_\delta, \tilde{\theta}, \tilde{\rho}\right) = \underset{\mathbf{x}_\delta, \theta, \rho}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{o=1}^8 \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}_o} \left[\iota_\ell - g_o(\mathbf{x}_\delta, \theta, \rho) m_\ell^{\text{pup}}(\rho^{-1} \mathbf{R}_\theta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_\delta)) \right]^2, \quad (29)$$

where \mathbf{R}_θ is the 2D rotation operator by the angle θ . Noting the subset of sub-apertures in the octant o , the octant gain is analytically given by

$$g_o(\mathbf{x}_\delta, \theta, \rho) = \frac{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}_o} \iota_\ell m_\ell^{\text{pup}}(\rho^{-1} \mathbf{R}_\theta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_\delta))}{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{V}_o} [m_\ell^{\text{pup}}(\rho^{-1} \mathbf{R}_\theta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_\delta))]^2}. \quad (30)$$

The residuals of Fig. 12a4 show that the pupil model including the spiders and the octant gains fits well the data: the gain and most of the spider patterns disappear. Because the `PupilMonitor` is limited by the subset \mathcal{V} of valid sub-apertures in the RTC (the blue area of Fig. 12a1 is not returned by the `LoopMonitor`), the model may miss important information for the magnification fit (the lateral registration is well constrained by the spider shadows). As discussed in Sec. 4.1, the question was raised to use the full pixel frame available in the `SpotMonitor` to obtain the flux in all sub-apertures to extend the fit on the edges, as shown in Figs. 13a1-a4.

Figure 12b1-b4 compares the estimated parameters from the `LoopMonitor` intensity telemetry (plain curves) and from the pixel stream (dashed curve). For the clocking, we only display the error δ_θ . Except for the magnification on GPAO2, all the estimations are in perfect agreement. This mainly comes from the fact that the photometric pupil is smaller than the SH-WFS field. If the magnification would have been positive (larger footprint of the photometric pupil), then using the full pixel frame could surely have been determining.

[§]Due to its poor resolution, the angle and magnification is not fitted for the 9×9 NGS IR mode.

[¶]In LGS mode, some sub-apertures are shared among two neighbouring octants. In this case, boxes are alternately attributed to each octant, as visible in Fig. 12c3

Figure 12. Fitting of the photometric pupil by the PupilMonitor in NGS VIS (a), NGS IR (b) and LGS (c). Panels a1,b1,c1: intensities streamed by the LoopMonitor, the data which are not measured are emphasised in blue (zero weight in the model fitting). Panels a2,b2,c2: high resolution VLT pupil, the model is averaged in each sub-aperture to down-sample it to the SH-WFS resolution (green grid). Panels a3,b3,c3: PupilMonitor model accounting for the OCAM2 octant gains (NGS VIS and LGS only). Panels a4,b4,c4: residuals.

Figure 13. Panels a2,a3,a4,a5: same as Fig. 12 but on the intensities obtained from the pixel frame on the full SH-WFS sensor (a1). Panels b1-b4: comparing the pupil model fitted in the LoopMonitor data (plain curves) and on the intensities derived from the average pixel frames (dashed curves). GPAO2 was running at gain medium, all others at gain high.

Concerning the mismatch of the GPAO2 magnification, let us insist here that the photometric pupil magnification is mainly constrained by the values in the sub-apertures on the pupil edge, that is to say the real flux signal compared to the background noise level of SPARTA that is 0-clipped. Thus, the estimated flux relative

to the background pedestal depends on the camera settings. In Fig. 12c4, all GPAOs were at gain high except GPAO2 (medium).

Figure 14. Photometric pupil parameters fitted on-sky by the PupilMonitor for the 40x40 NGS VIS and 9x9 NGS IR (first and second line, VLTI run of August 2025, 8 nights) and 30x30 LGS (third line, science verification of March 2026, 2 nights). The clocking parameter is displayed in terms of the angle parameter θ that evolves with the azimuth and elevation angles. The magnification parameter is displayed in terms of the elevation. The size of the dots is proportional to the equivalent wind speed v_0 fitted by the AtmPerfMonitor, see Sec. 5. The values between parentheses are the median values of each data clouds, also highlighted by the coloured dashed lines. In the NGS IR mode, the pupil magnification is not fitted and let equalled to the default value of 100 %.

The same conclusion on data acquired during the VLTI run of August 2025: the two regimes in the estimated magnification visible for the NGS VIS mode correspond to two camera gains: **high** and **medium**. An option would be to base the photometric pupil fit on the flux estimated by the SpotMonitor. This nonetheless implies to fit all the spots, and not only the subset \mathcal{V} mentioned in Sec. 4.1. In addition to be more time consuming, this implies the SpotMonitor module to run, which only happens in closed loop while the LoopMonitor always runs along with the SPARTA pipelines.

The LGS mode being always running with the same gain (**high**), it does not suffer from this issue, giving coherent results across all the datasets. Once again, it is possible to see that the photometric pupil scales with the elevation, a results which is consistent with what was observed with the MisregMonitor in Sec. 3.3, pointing towards a cross-talk with the SH-WFS focusing stage. Here as well, GPAO4 is the most concerned by this feature.

As a side remark, the magnification output by the PupilMonitor is also displayed in NGS IR but is useless. Indeed, with the 9x9 resolution, the model is not sensitive enough to accurately fit the magnification. Similarly, the clocking angle is poorly constrained, as shown by the large errors on δ_θ . After these tests during a VLTI run, it was decided to de-activate the clocking fit by the PupilMonitor in NGS IR.

The strong wobble of the photometric pupil that is visible on the lateral errors in NGS VIS and LGS demonstrates that it cannot be used for the PSIM mis-registration monitoring. These graphs also represent an independent validation of the ShiftMonitor closed loop system auto-alignment: it is clearly visible that in the NGS VIS, there is a bias on the pupil positioning that increases with the wind speed (see in particular the bottom

right of the figure). This bias is a measure of the error of the `ShiftMonitor` in presence of strong wind. We find here again the results of Sec. 3.2: the bias is less than 25 % SA.

Finally, the `PupilMonitor` is in charge to generate a dynamic subset of valid sub-apertures in the context of the LGS plume mitigation, see Fig. 15. The sub-apertures on the side of the SH-WFS pupil closed to the LLT can catch the Rayleigh diffusion of the laser beam in the atmosphere, so-called laser plume. Doing so, the AO loop converges towards an aberrant but stable state, see Figs. 15a,b. When detuning the laser so that the sodium layer is no more excited, the signal on the plume is clearly visible in the sub-apertures on the edge but within the controlled area, see Fig. 15c.

Figure 15. Plume mitigation strategy. Panel a: when using all sub-apertures, the AO loop can lock on the laser plume. Panel b: DM command pattern when locked on the laser plume. Panel c: detuned acquisition, the plume is visible on the left side. Panel d: the `PupilMonitor` is used to de-activate on-the-fly sub-apertures around the LLT position. Panel e: the loop is stable despite the plume being visible in the background of the spots of the sub-apertures on the edge.

The `PupilMonitor` is used to de-activate corrupted sub-apertures on-the-fly as the pupil rotates in front of the SH-WFS. Sub-apertures up to a radius of 7.5 sub-aperture pitch from the LLT are removed from the control loop. To keep the loop stable, the 20 first controlled modes are projected on these discarded sub-apertures by filtering the PSIM during its inversion when computing the control matrix. Doing so, the loop does not present instabilities on the discarded area, see Fig. 15e.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we presented some core modules of GPAO’s SRTC. The PSIM model, heart of the control matrix, implements a fine model of the ALPAO DM influence function that can efficiently reproduce the inter-actuator cross-talk generate pure tip-tilt and piston shape. More details on the model calibration will be the subject of a future communication, see Ref. [9].

GPAO commissioning was the opportunity to validate on-sky our new approach for pupil centring in open-loop via the `ShiftMonitor` with a perturbative approach. Results on the faint end of GPAO shows high SNR despite the use of less modes to be faster to compensate the slow frame rate. The closed loop estimator was also intensively tested. As predicted from simulations, when the combination of wind speed and loop rate is unfavourable, the auto-alignment could lead to loop instabilities and was thus de-activated. Nonetheless, for higher frame rates, the `ShiftMonitor` manages to keep the lateral error below 25 % of a sub-aperture and is a good proof of concept of the methods envisioned for the Extremely Large Telescope. Indeed, for the same number of actuators and WFS resolution running at 1 kHz, at the scale of the 39 m pupil the wind will be slower. These results are confirmed by the `MisregMonitor` that estimates the PSIM parameters from the loop telemetry. This is also the first time that its performances are presented for different loop settings. We demonstrated that it is more impacted by the wind than the `ShiftMonitor`, only providing quantitative results on the lateral errors when running at 1 kHz.

The new `SpotMonitor` represents a major new contribution for the operation of AO systems. It implements an inverse problem approach fitting a limited number of parameters that are jointly estimated across all the SH-WFS sub-apertures. Doing so makes it fast and extremely robust to noise. Its reliability has been exercised in operation across all the range of magnitudes required for GPAO and turbulence conditions at Paranal. The fit initialisation is computed via analytical formulas that can be solved with fast Fourier transforms on the full field of view. This allows to directly locate the global minimum at the pixel resolution before its fine optimisation. Via this method, we can make a good use of the large but very noisy field of view of the LO and find the NGS. We also use a global inverse problem approach to retrieve the sodium layer thickness from the spot elongation in LGS mode.

The `AtmPerfMonitor` of the AOF was augmented with a new multi-layer frozen flow estimator that can retrieve the wind speeds of the different turbulence layers. It is further described in Ref. [7]. The results show

that the turbulence at Paranal is generally dominated by strong frozen layer that carry most of the energy. This calls for new predictive methods that could use this information.

Finally the `PupilMonitor` tracks the photometric pupil. Initially for pure monitoring purposes (the photometric pupil is not GPAO's pupil reference that is the DM which has a larger clear aperture), it now plays a key role in the system to mitigate the impact of the laser plume in LGS mode and the camera gain monitoring.

On a general level, on the long run, having robust, precise and quantitative monitors can produce educated feedbacks on the AO system for possible improvements or save precious calibration time [22], or even help for data reduction. For example, a varying spot size can point towards a focusing issue with the SH-WFS lenslet arrays. The photometric wobble measurements can be used to realign the optical train. The results of the `AtmPerfMonitor` can be used as priors when reducing the instrument data based the quality of the AO performances. As a consequence, the implementation of methods based on the physics of the system to fit their parameters is a powerful way to extract meaningful and interpretable information on the system.

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Auto-calibration and performance monitoring of GRAVITY+ Adaptive Optics system with physics-based methods and inverse problem approaches

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Abstract

In 2024/2025, the GRAVITY+ Adaptive Optics (GPAO) project installed **four extreme AO systems on the 8-meter UTs of the Very Large Telescope**: 43x43 deformable mirrors (DM, 1432 actuators), 40x40 (1240 sub-apertures (SA)) visible and 30x30 (704 SA) laser guide star Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensors (SH-WFS) with 9x9 (60 SA) infrared or 2x2 (12 SA) visible SH-WFS for low order sensing. **These subsystems are distributed across the entire infrastructure** (pupil in M2 rotating with elevation; DM in Coudé train wobbling and rotating with azimuth; WFSs fixed on the ground; science focal plane in the interferometric laboratory 150 meters away). GPAO's complexity prefigures that of the AO systems of future giant telescopes: numerous modes, many moving components, and the need to operate robustly in a broad range of magnitudes and turbulence conditions. GPAO successfully achieved these goals thanks to a **complete re-design of the tools available in the Standard Platform for Adaptive Optics Real Time Applications (SPARTA, from ESO) and the development of new, versatile methods based on physical modelling and inverse problem approaches**. In this work we present the five main modules and their on-sky performances: (i) the **Pseudo-Synthetic Interaction Matrix (PSIM) module**, in charge to numerically (and quickly) compensate the system rotation, which includes a physical model of the ALPAO DM influence functions, (ii) the **Innovative estimators of WFS/DM lateral mis-registrations** for the instrument bootstrapping through the turbulence in open loop and its auto-alignment in closed loop, (iii) a **robust spot monitor for faint star detection and centering** during the automatic acquisition sequence and for the **update of the weighted center of gravity in closed loop**, (iv) the **atmospheric and performance monitor** made versatile to the different GPAO modes and augmented with an innovative multi-layer profiler for wind estimation, and (v) a **pupil monitor** that offers a fine positioning of the photometric pupil, its orientation and magnification.

1. PSIM – Pseudo-Synthetic Interaction Matrix DM/WFS

1.1 DM influence function model

1.2 SH-WFS model and interaction matrix (IM) mis-registration

2. Shift/MisregMonitor – auto-calibration / monitoring

2.1 Lateral registration during acquisition [1]

2.2 Closed loop auto-alignment [1] and mis-registration monitoring [2,3]

3. SpotMonitor – Robust spot detection and monitoring

Global inverse problem approach on Ω_{SA} SA subset: $\Rightarrow d_s$: s-th SA pixel box / W_s : valid pixel map $\Rightarrow p$: 2D Gaussian pattern of 2D position ρ_s , 2D FWHM $\theta_s = (\theta_{s,||}, \theta_{s,\perp}, \theta_s)$, and amplitude α_s , $\Rightarrow \beta$: global offset (noise O-clipping by SPARTA).

$$\text{argmin}_{(\theta_s), (\rho_s), (\alpha_s), \beta} \sum_{s \in \Omega_{SA}} \|d_s - (\alpha_s \cdot p(\theta_s, \rho_s) + \beta)\|_{W_s}^2$$

3.1 Robust star detection and centering: common spot fitting

3.2 Spot monitoring: global model fitting

Global model: $\forall s \in \Omega_{SA} \Rightarrow$ individual $\{\rho_s\}, \{\alpha_s\}, \Rightarrow$ shared β , \Rightarrow shared spot parameters for high SNR estimation.

- Case 1 – natural guide star: \Rightarrow 1 spot size θ_0 , \Rightarrow shared β , \Rightarrow shared spot parameters for high SNR estimation.
- Case 2 – extended object: \Rightarrow 2 spot sizes θ_0, θ_{\perp} , \Rightarrow 1 orientation θ
- Case 3 – laser guide star (θ_s given by laser launch telescope position): \Rightarrow 1 laser size $\theta_{L,s}$, \Rightarrow 1 sodium layer thickness Na_{th} (spot elongation θ_{\parallel}).

4. AtmPerfMonitor – turbulence characterization

5. PupilMonitor – Following photometric pupil

References & Acknowledgments

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